

THE STUDY OF THE ORKHON-YENISEI MONUMENTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20846366>

Uzbek philology also occupies an important place in the comprehensive study of ancient Turkic written monuments as a unique linguistic and cultural heritage, including their translation into modern language, reading, interpretation, explanation, and commentary. Among Uzbek scholars, Abdurauf Fitrat, Olim Sharafiddinov, Aziz Qayumov, Alibek Rustamov, G'ani Abdurahmonov, and Nasimxon Rahmonov have carried out significant research on this subject. First of all, these ancient inscriptions were translated from Old Turkic into modern Uzbek. In this regard, the contributions of Alibek Rustamov, Aziz Qayumov, G'ani Abdurahmonov, Natan Mallayev, Qosimjon Sodiqov, Nasimxon Rahmonov, and Boqijon To'xliyev are particularly noteworthy.

Olim Sharafiddinov literary scholar and author of literature textbooks for grades 6–9 of general secondary schools, O. Sharafiddinov also provided information about ancient songs, myths, and legends and attempted to analyze some of them. The anthology of literature he compiled, covering the period from the earliest stages of Uzbek literature to the works of Alisher Navoi, was of great significance in its time. Speaking about the role and importance of these manuals, Aziz Qayumov, who devoted himself to studying the earliest examples of Turkic literature and conducted extensive research on this period, emphasized that he had greatly benefited from Olim Sharafiddinov's books.

G'ani Abdurahmonov and Alibek Rustamov G'ani Abdurahmonov and Alibek Rustamov are distinguished scholars who conducted scientific research on translating the Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions from Old Turkic into modern Uzbek and thereby made a worthy contribution to Uzbek Turkology. A significant event was the publication of their textbook *Ancient Turkic Language* in 1982 for university students. The textbook provides detailed information on the ancient forms and structure of the Turkic language.

In addition to the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments, the textbook also introduces less-studied sources such as *The Story of Princes Kalyanankara and Papamkara*, *Sekiz Yukmak*, and *The Legend of the Demon Atavaka*. The phonetics, graphics, morphology, and syntax of the ancient Turkic language are analyzed philologically. The section entitled "Texts" contains theoretical information about the Tonyukuk inscription, the Kül Tegin inscription, the Minor and Major inscriptions, the Bilge Khagan inscription, and the Ungin (Ongin) inscriptions, together with their contents and transcriptions.

Natan Mallayev the literary scholar N. Mallayev included information on the discovery, study, and literary value of the Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions in the chapter "The Most Ancient Literary Monuments" of his textbook *History of Uzbek Literature* for higher educational institutions. In addition to providing general information about the inscriptions, the scholar also drew scientific conclusions about them. In particular, he wrote:

“The Orkhon-Yenisei monuments are not only linguistic and written monuments but also historical sources. They provide valuable materials and information for studying the socio-economic life of the fifth to eighth centuries and acquaint us with the customs, beliefs, and traditions of various Turkic peoples and tribes. The Orkhon-Yenisei monuments also possess considerable artistic value. Besides containing many poetic lines, some prose passages sound like poetry, and certain historical events are depicted in an artistic style using various literary devices. The artistic significance of the elegies on the tombstones is especially remarkable. Through them, we become familiar with the inner emotional experiences of the mourners. Therefore, S.Y.Malov called the fifth-century Yenisei monuments cemetery poetry.”

These views indicate that the scholar's conclusions resulted from studying poetic elements in the inscriptions, such as alliteration, assonance, repetition, rhyme, and various figurative devices. Mallayev's research in this field serves not only Uzbek Turkology but also world Turkology as an important scientific, historical, and theoretical source for discovering, studying, translating, commenting upon, compiling dictionaries of, and publishing ancient Turkic written monuments.

Qosimjon Sodiqov Qosimjon Sodiqov is a meticulous researcher who made an enormous contribution to studying the genesis, language, and culture of ancient Turkic monuments. He can rightfully be considered one of the leading representatives of Uzbek Turkology and a dedicated scholar who devoted a significant part of his academic career to researching rare sources connected with the ancient layers of Uzbek literature.

For many years at the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies (now a university), he taught courses such as *History of the Uzbek Language*, *Ancient Turkic Alphabets*, *The Language of Turkic Written Monuments*, and *Religion and Philosophical Life of the Ancient Turks*. At the same time, he authored scholarly works, textbooks, and teaching aids on the rich spiritual heritage, language, history, literature, and culture of our ancestors.

The transcriptions and Uzbek translations prepared by Qosimjon Sodiqov of the *Kül Tegin Inscription*, *Tonyukuk Inscription*, *Bilge Khagan Inscription*, and *Irq Bitig* significantly enriched our understanding of the internal structure and distinctive features of the ancient Turkic language, as well as the history of ancient Turkic written literature, transforming many assumptions into substantiated scientific conclusions.

Boqijon To'xliyev in the chapters “The Most Ancient Uzbek Literature” and “Ancient Songs” of his literature textbook for tenth-grade students, Boqijon To'xliyev consistently presents information about the discovery, volume, content, events, and literary value of the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments. While discussing their study, the scholar also expresses his views that the ancient periods of Uzbek literary history constitute an integral part of pre-Islamic Turkic literature. He notes the research carried out in this field and lists the names of Uzbek and international scholars who contributed significantly to the study of the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments, providing a general assessment of their achievements.

Eldar Asanov thanks to independence, the history of our people, our literary heritage, and the roots of our national identity, including ancient Turkic monuments and particularly the Orkhon-Yenisei written monuments, have begun to receive attention at the level of state policy. Despite the complexity and difficulty of this field, the expansion of research and improvement of conditions have led to quantitative and qualitative changes in scholarship. The number of

scholars devoted to this field has increased, and new generations of talented young researchers have emerged. One of them is Eldar Asanov.

In his dissertation entitled *The Language of the Central Asian Turkic-Runic Inscriptions*, Asanov proposed a new classification of these monuments based on cultural and political factors. He divided them into smaller groups such as Semirechye, Syr Darya, Sogdiana, and Eastern Kazakhstan according to their geographical location and other factors.

Of particular importance is his finding that twenty monuments previously considered part of these groups had actually been written in other alphabets. Through a re-examination of thirteen inscriptions, he identified several rare words and introduced them into scholarly circulation.

Furthermore, the scholar demonstrated that the Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions exhibit features of two different dialects: one characteristic of the language of the Orkhon inscriptions and the other closer to the language of the Yenisei inscriptions. The phonetic, lexical, and morphological differences between the two groups were thoroughly analyzed in his research.

According to Asanov: "The Orkhon and Yenisei alphabets contain ligatures indicating double consonants and a number of ideograms expressing frequently used syllables and morphemes. In the Fergana, Tashkent, and Kashkadarya inscriptions, only the ligatures *ič-či*, while in Munchoqtepa-2 the forms *ny* and *nt* occur. The following ligatures appear in the Semirechye Turkic-runic inscriptions: *nč1*, *nč2*, and *oq-qo*. The remaining ligatures have not been recorded in the Central Asian Turkic-runic inscriptions".

This statement clearly demonstrates the depth of the scholar's research.

The scientific studies conducted by Uzbek scholars clearly demonstrate that the historical roots of ancient Turkic written monuments are deeply connected with Uzbekistan. Studying these monuments from various perspectives and utilizing this ancient heritage in the creation of the culture of New Uzbekistan remains one of the important tasks of our time.

Our studies, observations, and comparative analyses show that substantial research has been carried out in this field in Uzbekistan. Numerous scholarly and literary works, textbooks, anthologies, collections, and lecture materials have been prepared and published, and significant achievements have been made in translating and interpreting these monuments.

Ancient Turkic written monuments belong to very early and diverse periods of our past. Consequently, their language and script are also extremely ancient and varied. From this perspective, although considerable achievements have been made in translating various words and terms into modern Uzbek, certain ambiguities and shortcomings still remain. It is hoped that such deficiencies will be eliminated in future research and typological studies of ancient Turkic written monuments.

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